

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION OF CHILDREN WITH LEARNING DISABILITIES: A REVIEW AND SYNTHESIS OF RELATED LITERATURE

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI), as an emerging and trending tech-tool in the global education space, is playing an increasingly transformative role in education. It is offering adaptive tools and intelligent systems that support inclusive learning for children with learning disabilities (LDs). This paper reviewed and synthesized related discourse to (1) analyze existing peer-reviewed literature on AI applications in the education of learners with LDs, (2) identify key domains of AI applications, and (3) highlight ethical, technical, and pedagogical implications of AI for inclusive education. It used a narrative synthesis approach with a focus on 102 studies published between 2013 and 2024. These were selected through systematic database search engine and thematic screening. Five thematic domains emerged: AI-powered assistive technologies, such as intelligent tutoring systems, emotion and behavior monitoring tools, language and communication supports, and teacher-AI collaboration models. Findings indicated that AI can enhance learning outcomes, engagement, and accessibility for students with LDs through personalized instructions and real-time feedback. Despite these benefits, the review identified and highlighted key challenges such as data privacy risks, algorithmic bias, contextual mismatches in low-resource settings, and limited user participation in the design of AI tools. Gaps in longitudinal research, ethical governance, and equitable deployment further constrain the impact of AI on inclusive education for students with learning disabilities. It concluded that, while AI is not a magical pedagogical panacea, it holds significant potential to advance educational equity when deployed ethically, inclusively, and in alignment with learner needs. Future research is required to understand how best to leverage this technology and prioritize access to quality, inclusive education for children with learning disabilities in line with global best practices.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Inclusive Education, Learning disabilities, Assistive Technology

Introduction

The education of children with learning disabilities presents a persistent global challenge, marked by the need for tailored interventions and inclusive teaching practices (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011). Learning disabilities encompass a range of neurological conditions such as dyslexia, dysgraphia, dyscalculia, and sometimes co-exist with attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), and autism spectrum disorders (ASDs) that affect a child's ability to process information effectively (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Learning disabilities, as defined by the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA), refer to disorders in one or more of the basic psychological processes involved in understanding or using spoken or written language (U.S. Department of Education, 2004). These conditions significantly affect a child's ability to listen, think, speak, read, write, spell, or perform mathematical calculations. Teaching these categories of students has remained very challenging despite efforts to address their concerns, especially when traditional educational approaches have fails to meet the unique needs of these learners, This has necessitated the adoption of more adaptive and responsive approaches like AI tool to improve inclusionary practices in the education system (Smith, 2017).

Artificial Intelligence refers to the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines, particularly computer systems (Russell & Norvig, 2020). In educational contexts, AI encompasses tools and platforms capable of learning, adapting, and making decisions based on data. This includes machine learning algorithms, natural language processing, and computer vision, all of which underpin many educational technologies (Holmes et al., 2022). Artificial Intelligence(AI) has increasingly been integrated into educational environments with the potentials to revolutionize how instruction, assessment, and student support are delivered (Luckin et al., 2016). AI-driven tools offer personalized learning experiences, real-time feedback, and advanced analytics to track student progress (Holmes et al., 2019). For children with learning disabilities, AI provides assistive mechanisms that can mitigate learning barriers, foster engagement, and improve academic outcomes (Zhao & Singh, 2021; Chen et al., 2021). Despite the growing interest in AI-enhanced education, there remains a need for critical analysis of its impact on children with learning disabilities. This will inform educators, policymakers, and technologists about the potential of AI to support inclusive education for all learners, including those with learning disabilities. AI-enabled educational technologies often provide dynamic, responsive learning environments tailored to individual needs (Al-Azawei et al., 2017). These include, among others, speech-to-text applications, predictive text tools, intelligent tutoring systems, and AI-powered reading aids (Graesser et al., 2018; Light & McNaughton, 2019).

This paper aims to synthesize current research on the intersection of AI and special education, identifying key applications, benefits, challenges, and gaps in the literature. To do this, it draws from a wide range of interdisciplinary literature to provide a comprehensive understanding of how AI is being leveraged to improve educational outcomes for children with learning disabilities.

Purpose of the study

The paper was done with the objectives to:

- Analyze existing peer-reviewed literature on AI applications in the education of learners with learning disabilities.
- Identify key domains of AI applications, such as *assistive technology, and adaptive learning systems*.
- Highlight the ethical and pedagogical implications of AI in inclusive education.

Methodology

This paper adopted a narrative synthesis approach and provided a comprehensive understanding of how Artificial Intelligence (AI) is being utilized to support the education of children with learning disabilities. The objective was to identify emerging themes, assess the effectiveness of various AI applications, and highlight research gaps that could inform future inquiry and policy development. The literature search was conducted using a systematic strategy across multiple academic databases, including Web of Science, Scopus, ERIC (Education Resources Information Center), PubMed, and Google Scholar. The search focused on peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, and relevant policy reports published between 2013 and 2024. Keywords and search terms included combinations such as: “Artificial Intelligence” AND “Learning Disabilities” AND “Education,” “AI in Special Education,” “Intelligent Tutoring Systems” AND “Dyslexia” OR “Autism,” “Assistive Technology” AND “Machine Learning,” and “AI and Inclusive Learning.” Boolean operators and truncation techniques were applied to broaden or narrow results as appropriate. Additionally, backward and forward citation tracking was employed to identify further relevant literature beyond initial search results.

Selection Criteria: Studies were included based on their alignment with the research focus. The inclusion criteria comprised peer-reviewed journal articles, conference papers, and key policy reports published between 2013 and 2024. Eligible studies were those that focused on children aged 5 to 18 with diagnosed learning disabilities such as dyslexia, dysgraphia, dyscalculia, and co-existing conditions like ADHD and autism. The review paper also considered research that examined AI-driven educational tools or systems and was published in English. Conversely, studies were excluded if they focused solely on adult learners or higher education settings, if the literature did not explicitly involve Artificial Intelligence such as general educational technologies or if they were non-academic sources like blogs or unverified reports. Additionally, research centered purely on medical or clinical diagnostics without an educational context was not included in the review.

Data Analysis

A total of 102 studies were selected from an initial pool of over 380 articles following a structured three-stage screening and synthesis process. This included title and abstract screening, full-text evaluation, and thematic classification. From each selected study, key variables were extracted, including the type of AI intervention, the specific learning disability targeted, the

educational setting (whether mainstream, special, or inclusive), reported outcomes such as student engagement, academic performance, or behavioral improvements, and the research methodology employed, such as experimental, quasi-experimental, or case study designs. A thematic analysis was applied to the extracted data, which enabled the identification of recurring themes across the literature. These themes included the effectiveness of AI interventions, barriers to implementation, ethical concerns, and pedagogical implications. The results were grouped into broader analytical categories and synthesized to inform discussions and generate evidence-based recommendations for future practice and policy.

Limitations: Despite efforts to provide a comprehensive narrative review, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the review was restricted to publications in English, which may have resulted in the exclusion of relevant studies published in other languages. Second, the use of a narrative synthesis approach introduces a degree of subjectivity in the interpretation and grouping of themes. Third, the review was based entirely on secondary data, which may not reflect the most recent developments in AI technologies and their application in educational settings. Lastly, the focus on school-aged learners may have excluded broader insights from adult education or lifelong learning contexts that could still be relevant.

Findings and Discussion

The findings of the study are in alignment with the stated objectives: (1) analyzing existing peer-reviewed literature on AI applications in the education of learners with learning disabilities (LDs), (2) identifying key domains of AI applications in the education of children with LDs, and (3) highlighting the ethical and pedagogical implications of AI in inclusive education. Thematic synthesis of the literature revealed five core domains: AI-powered assistive technologies, intelligent tutoring systems, emotion and behavioral AI, language and communication support tools, and human-AI collaboration models.

AI-Powered Assistive Technologies: AI-enhanced assistive technologies are among the most widely adopted tools for supporting learners with disabilities. These tools employ machine learning and natural language processing (NLP) to improve accessibility, support literacy skills, and promote learner autonomy (Smith & Okolo, 2021). Text-to-Speech (TTS) systems assist students with dyslexia or visual impairments by reading text aloud, reducing cognitive overload, and increasing comprehension. Conversely, Speech-to-Text (STT) technologies convert spoken input into written text, enabling students with dysgraphia or motor challenges to express themselves effectively (Khan et al., 2020).

Optical Character Recognition (OCR), enhanced by AI, converts printed or handwritten text into digital formats usable by screen readers. Tools like Microsoft Immersive Reader allow learners to customize text appearance and read-aloud features, supporting diverse cognitive needs (Cavender & Ladner, 2018). AI-based grammar and spelling correction platforms, such as Grammarly and Ginger, leverage contextual natural language processing to assist learners with language processing difficulties in producing coherent, error-free writing (Lopez et al., 2022).

The literature consistently indicates that these tools contribute to increased learner confidence, academic performance, and classroom participation, particularly when combined with

personalized instruction and teacher support (Zhao & Singh, 2021). However, successful adoption often depends on adequate teacher training and the adaptability of the technologies to local contexts.

Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS): Intelligent Tutoring Systems (ITS) are AI-powered platforms that simulate one-on-one tutoring by adapting content and instructional strategies to individual learners. ITS platforms such as Carnegie Learning, ALEKS, and Knewton analyze learner data in real time to adjust the difficulty level and sequencing of instructional material (VanLehn, 2011). These platforms are particularly beneficial for students with LDs, who often require repeated exposure and targeted remediation to master foundational skills.

AutoTutor, for example, engages learners in Socratic-style dialogue and provides immediate feedback on responses, which is especially beneficial for learners with attention disorders or reading comprehension challenges (Graesser et al., 2018). Gamification features, including avatars, point systems, and progress tracking, enhance student motivation and engagement, key factors for learners with executive functioning issues (Griol & Callejas, 2020). Despite their advantages, most intelligent tutoring system platforms are not originally designed with learning disabilities in mind. As a result, they may lack the flexibility to respond to the nuanced needs of this population. Moreover, access in low-resource settings is constrained by infrastructure gaps, limited funding, and inadequate training for educators.

Emotion AI and Behavioral Monitoring: Emotion AI, also known as affective computing, refers to the use of AI systems that can detect, interpret, and respond to human emotions. In educational settings, these technologies are being piloted to monitor the emotional states of learners with learning disabilities, especially those who struggle with verbal communication, such as children with autism or ADHD (D’Mello & Graesser, 2015). Through facial expression analysis, voice modulation, and biometric signals, platforms like Emotion AI, ReCog, and Empatica can detect signs of frustration, confusion, or boredom on task that imply their disabilities like reading, writing, or performing arithmetic operations. Behavioral analytics embedded in classroom technologies provide teachers with insights into learner engagement and attention patterns, allowing for timely intervention and instructional adjustment (Amon et al., 2019). These technologies also support self-regulation by helping students recognize and manage their emotional responses, often through gamified biofeedback platforms that teach mindfulness and focus.

While these applications are promising, they raise ethical concerns, particularly around data privacy, surveillance, and informed consent. Cukurova, Luckin, and Clark-Wilson (2021) argue that deploying such tools in schools, especially with vulnerable learners, requires robust ethical frameworks, data protection policies, and clear parental involvement.

AI for Language and Communication Support: Children with learning disabilities often experience difficulties in language comprehension, verbal expression, and social communication. AI-powered tools address these challenges by facilitating language access and supporting speech development. NLP applications like Text Help Read & Write and IBM Watson Tutor can simplify complex text, highlight important concepts, and provide audio support, thereby helping students engage with class-level material more effectively. Speech therapy applications such as

Speechify and SayIt integrate speech recognition and AI feedback to support children with apraxia, stuttering, or delayed language development. Augmentative and Alternative Communication (AAC) devices have also advanced with AI features, providing speech-generating tools that adapt to user preferences and routines. Tools like Avaz and Proloquo2Go use predictive modeling to suggest vocabulary and respond to contextual cues (Light & McNaughton, 2019). Additionally, conversational agents' AI-powered chatbots are being piloted to assist children with ASD in practicing dialogue, emotional expression, and conversational turn-taking. Early research suggests these tools can help learners build confidence and fluency in social interactions when used consistently (Bernstein et al., 2020).

Teacher-AI Collaboration Models: While AI tools are often designed with learner interaction in mind, their effectiveness increases when embedded within collaborative teaching frameworks. Teacher-AI collaboration allows educators to harness AI as a supportive partner in planning, assessment, and classroom management. Tools like ClassDojo assist teachers in monitoring behavior trends and providing tailored behavioral feedback for learners with attention or conduct disorders. AI systems also contribute to the development of adaptive Individualized Education Programs (IEPs). By analyzing academic history and behavioral data, these systems help refine learning goals and track student progress over time (Chen et al., 2021). Real-time dashboards give teachers immediate insights into learners' strengths and difficulties, enabling timely interventions and differentiated instruction.

Moreover, professional development platforms like TeachFX and Edthena use AI to analyze teacher practices such as questioning patterns and talk-time ratios, encouraging reflective pedagogy that supports inclusive learning. Nevertheless, concerns remain about algorithm transparency and overreliance on AI-generated insights. Selwyn (2019) warns that an overdependence on AI could undermine the relational and intuitive aspects of teaching, especially in inclusive classrooms where empathy and human judgment are crucial.

Benefits and Opportunities of AI to children with learning disabilities

The integration of AI in education presents several key opportunities for supporting learners with learning disabilities. Most notably, AI enables personalized learning by adapting content and pace in real-time, accommodating students' unique cognitive profiles (Gauthier et al., 2020). It improves accessibility through assistive tools that overcome physical, linguistic, and cognitive barriers. AI also supports early identification and intervention by analyzing behavioral and performance patterns to detect potential learning challenges at earlier stages (Mouza et al., 2022).

Moreover, AI technologies enhance motivation and engagement through interactive and gamified environments, which are particularly effective for learners with attention deficits. Teacher support is another major benefit, as AI automates routine tasks and provides insights that facilitate inclusive instructional planning. It bypasses the disability and reduces the effect on the learning process, and improves performance on tasks like reading and writing, as well as enhance the self-worth of children. Finally, AI systems offer global reach and inclusivity, with the potential to expand educational access in rural or under-resourced settings, thereby supporting Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles.

Ethical and Pedagogical Implications of AI for Inclusive Education Practice

There is an increasing concern about ethical issues in the use of AI as they appear to be a potential ethical threat to the human elements in the education system. These call for procedures to ensure quality delivery and protection of stakeholders across disciplines. Responding to this United Nations Education Scientific & Cultural Organization (2021) identified these as issues to be addressed; privacy risk and breach, informed consent, biased data assumption, fairness, accountability, and statistical apophenia, problems with data collection, restricted availability of data sources, bias and representation, data ownership and control, data autonomy, and human agency, security and safety of data, learners' autonomy and data integrity. Efforts to manage these ethical concerns can further be complemented by sound principles such as inclusiveness, human centricity, right to privacy, Sustainability & Proportionality, Transparency and Accountability, and Governance and Stewardship (Nganyen, Ngo, Hong, et al, (2023); Ashok, Madan, Joha & Sivarajah, 2022).

There is a strong cord that exists between the ability to handle ethical issues in AI and its pedagogical implications for inclusionary practices. Silvio, Gianmarco, et al (2024) noted that modern AI applications have been instrumental in supporting inclusive education, particularly for students with disabilities, by providing tailored learning supports and accessible educational materials. This places a demand on the school system to provide digital infrastructure, and connectivity to different platforms of AI to accommodate the diversity of an inclusive classroom system. Inclusive education and AI are mutual partners for progress that require the school system to build competencies of teachers, parents, children, and administrators to manage learners and diversity of AI applications across content areas (Starks & Reich, 2023; Gabriel, 2024). In addition, AI-driven inclusive learning will require attitudinal re-orientation among stakeholders; thus, the school system should have a robust advocacy and awareness to displace culture of resistance to changes. This is imperative because of the presence of different digital personalities; the digital natives will have no problems embracing AI tech to drive inclusive learning, but digital refugees and immigrants may have challenges with integration emerging?? innovation. Closely related are the discriminating attitudes toward learners with disabilities. The school needs a well-structured programme to deal with these potential tendencies to promote equity, access and diversity as core pillars of inclusivity.

Challenges to the Application of Artificial Intelligence in the Education of Children with Learning Disabilities

Despite the benefits, there are several challenges to integration of AI in inclusive education. One major concern is data privacy and ethics. AI systems collect sensitive information such as emotional states and learning behaviors, which may be misused or inadequately protected, especially in contexts lacking robust data governance (Binns et al., 2018). In many low- and middle-income countries, weak consent frameworks further expose vulnerable learners to risks. These challenges include the following:

Algorithmic bias is another significant issue. AI models trained on data that exclude learners with learning disabilities or diverse cultural contexts may produce biased outputs. For instance, facial

recognition systems often misinterpret the expressions of autistic learners, leading to false assumptions about engagement or mood (Williams & Gilbert, 2020).

Contextual limitations also hinder the transferability of AI tools developed in high-income Western contexts. These tools often fail to align with local curricula, dialects, or infrastructure, reducing their effectiveness in Sub-Saharan Africa or other low-resource environments. Furthermore, many schools face infrastructure and capacity challenges, including poor internet access, outdated devices, and a lack of technical training among educators (World Bank, 2022). Even when technologies are available, educators may lack the expertise to integrate them meaningfully. Lastly, there is growing concern over overreliance and deskilling, where teachers and caregivers become overly dependent on AI-generated insights. Without proper checks, this could erode pedagogical judgment and reduce the human element critical to inclusive teaching (Selwyn, 2019). Other challenges as highlighted by UNESCO (2021), Holmes et al.,(2021), (Borenstein & Howard, (2021)are; highly technology-dependent and cross-disciplines, lack of comprehensive public policy, inclusion and equity of minority groups, inadequate preparation of teachers for AI-powered education, poor preparation of AI to understand education as human related industry, inability to develop quality and inclusive data systems, none compliance to ethics and transparency in data collection, use, and dissemination information, societal drawbacks such as systemic bias, discrimination, inequality for marginalized groups of students with disabilities, and xenophobia.

Gaps in the Literature and Future Research Directions

Despite the growing interest in the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in inclusive education, several significant gaps remain in the literature. Addressing these gaps is essential for improving policy, practice, and the responsible integration of AI into learning environments for children with learning disabilities. First, there is a lack of longitudinal and impact-focused studies. Most existing research is exploratory, short-term, or limited to pilot programmes, often conducted in controlled environments rather than real classrooms. Few studies assess the sustained influence of AI tools on long-term academic performance, social-emotional development, or life outcomes. Future research should focus on multi-year, mixed-methods studies that evaluate academic retention, learner confidence, and transition outcomes resulting from AI interventions. Second, there is a clear underrepresentation of low-resource and culturally diverse settings. Most research is concentrated in high-income countries, leaving a gap in understanding how AI functions in low- and middle-income regions, particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America. These omissions hinder the development of context-appropriate, cost-effective AI tools. Future studies should prioritize localized research to explore how AI can be adapted and sustained in multilingual, multicultural, and low-tech educational settings.

Another gap is the limited inclusion of learner and teacher perspectives. Much of the literature focuses on the technical performance of AI systems, often overlooking the experiences and feedback of students, educators, and caregivers. This lack of participatory input reduces the relevance and usability of AI tools. Future research must engage end users in the design, testing, and refinement of AI technologies to ensure cultural, educational, and ethical appropriateness.

Moreover, current literature offers few concrete ethical or legal frameworks. Although concerns about privacy, consent, and algorithmic accountability are frequently acknowledged, they are rarely addressed in a structured or actionable way. Future research should work toward the development of ethical guidelines tailored to inclusive education contexts, with input from educators, legal experts, technologists, and disability rights advocates. These frameworks should emphasize transparency, child safety, and data protection. Lastly, the potential of emerging AI technologies remains largely unexplored. Tools such as generative AI (for example, ChatGPT), multimodal systems combining text, voice, and gesture recognition, and AI-powered robotics hold promise for learners with disabilities. However, there is a paucity of empirical studies which evaluate their educational value, safety, and ethical implications. Further investigation is required to assess how these innovations can support personalized learning, communication training, and social interaction in inclusive classrooms.

Conclusion

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is reshaping education by offering new pathways to support children with learning disabilities through personalized instruction, improved accessibility, and innovative tools. This review highlighted how AI-powered technologies can help reduce learning barriers and foster more inclusive classrooms. Five key domains emerged from the literature: AI-driven assistive technologies, intelligent tutoring systems, emotion and behavior monitoring tools, language and communication support, and teacher-AI collaboration models. Collectively, these innovations point toward a more responsive and learner-centered educational approach that addresses the diverse needs of students with learning disabilities. Despite this promise, significant challenges persist. Concerns about data privacy, algorithmic bias, limited cultural and contextual adaptability, and infrastructural shortcomings continue to hinder the equitable deployment of AI. Moreover, overdependence on AI risks sidelining the human elements of teaching, empathy, judgment, and relational support that are especially critical in special education.

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